

ENSURING INFORMATION SECURITY FOR YOUNG PEOPLE: GENERAL PROVISIONS AND PRINCIPLES

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Annotation: This article discusses the general provisions, priority areas and principles for ensuring information security of young people as a factor in the stable development of modern society.

Key words: information security, globalization of the information space, Internet addiction, online communication, digitalization, Maslahatchi consultants, threats in the information environment.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматриваются общие положения, приоритетные направления и принципы обеспечения информационной безопасности молодежи как фактора стабильного развития современного общества.

Ключевые слова: информационная безопасность, глобализация информационного пространства, интернет-зависимость, онлайн-коммуникация, цифровизация, консультанты Маслахатчи, угрозы в информационной среде.

Modern trends in social life in Uzbekistan are associated with the process of globalization of the information space, which creates new challenges in the formation of personality. Thanks to modern computer technologies, ambiguous, contradictory information is rapidly spreading, both positive, creative and negative, aggressive in nature, often with a distortion of moral norms and criteria, associated with inadequate social stereotypes and attitudes. The problem of information security therefore arises primarily for children, who currently have access to the Internet in most families in Uzbekistan. Currently, the issues of the influence of the Internet, computer technology on the individual, Internet addiction, the psychological dependence of the individual on the search for information are relevant. Communication on the network and other types of human activity in the information space of the Internet. According to observations of psychologists and taking into account the ever-growing audience of the network, the problem of Internet addiction is becoming more and more fundamental for the information society and in the future will play an

increasingly significant role in the mental health of a person in a society of universal digitalization.

In the field of Internet psychology, numerous studies are being carried out that show that constant use of the Internet not only at work, but also at home leads to a reduction in family communication, a breakdown in social ties, and depression. The result of alienation from friends, relatives, and family members is an increase in the number of mental disorders, an increase in crime, including in the field of Internet technologies, sexual perversions and other types of deviant behavior. These psychological phenomena negatively affect family relationships and reduce or neutralize the educational and other functions of the family. Therefore, in general, it is necessary to implement a wide range of targeted measures to further strengthen and develop the institution of the family, as the basis of society, President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Mirziyoyev Sh.M. signed the Decree No. UP 27 of February 28, 2023 according to which, during the implementation of the adopted state program for the implementation of the development strategy of the new Uzbekistan for 2022-2026, 2023 was declared the "Year of caring for people and quality education." In accordance with this program, on March 1, 2022, Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PP - 147 was adopted, according to which, in the administrative and support structure of the Makhalla, a specialist should be strengthened. The role of the older generation in the education and upbringing of youth - these are Makhalla advisors-maslahatchis, on whose shoulders lies such a responsible task as the upbringing of the younger generation.

The activities of Maslahatchi women can be carried out both at the level of direct social work and at the level of organizational, managerial and administrative activities: in partnership with institutions and organizations of the social protection system, public education, healthcare, district, the City and regional Khokimiyats, public organizations and associations. Taking into account the characteristics of potential "clients", maslahatchi, as a social worker, must have certain psychological skills. Maslahatchi, as a leader - teacher, assistant, coach, must have and constantly improve the following personal qualities: mastering the basics of computer skill; accept the worse of every person and respect their rights; tolerance; empathy, the ability to communicate with people, building trusting relationships, the ability to work in stressful situations, the ability to recognize and develop the strengths of people and families having self-control and the ability to manage their emotions and to change and control their behavior.

Maslahatchi plays an important role in increasing the spiritual and moral potential of families and young people as well as in matters of religious education. In the “youth-family-makhalla-society” system, it is necessary to establish effective work to ensure information security of young people, which can be carried out by mahalla consultants. As part of the interaction between the “makhalla family and the educational institution,” with the involvement of parents and teachers, they can carry out educational and preventive work on information security issues and prevent negative phenomena associated with information threats. In this context, makhalla consultants must have knowledge of age-sensitive periods for information security design. It must be taken into account that the most sensitive period for the development of computer and Internet addiction that is, for the formation of the necessary knowledge and skills in information security, is primary school age is when children have a strong sense of family, they are trusting and do not doubt the authority, but at the same time, have a natural desire to find out what they can afford to do without their parents’ permission. The mahalla advisor should draw the attention of adults to the fact that for the full development of the child it is necessary to teach the child to adequately perceive and evaluate information and to critically evaluate it on the basis of national and universal, moral and cultural values understand. It is completely natural for them to figure out what they can afford to do without parental permission. The mahalla advisor should draw the attention of adults to the fact that for the full development of the child it is necessary to teach the child to adequately perceive and evaluate information and to critically evaluate it on the basis of national and universal, moral and cultural values understand.

Mahalla counselors must have competence in the following areas:

1. Mental and physical health of children when working on computers, including aspects such as computer radiation, gymnastic exercises;
2. Hygienic requirements for the use of a home computer, taking into account issues of workplace organization, safety requirements for working at a computer, workplace lighting, electrical safety, influence of electromagnetic fields and radiation, noise and vibration;
3. Prevention of posture and vision problems when working at the computer with a suggestion for a series of exercises for the eyes and a way of working at the computer;

4. The negative impact of the computer on the mental health of children, taking into account the problem of stress when working with a computer and ways to prevent and correct it;

5. Social, emotional and personal aspects of computer activities, where counselors should inform parents about development, the influence of video games on the development of intelligence, learning and creating in the electronic environment, the influence of the computer on motivation, computer addiction, about the possibilities of using computers to increase motivation;

6. Information ethics and legal aspects of information protection with coverage of information security issues, Maslahatchi advisor on threats in the information environment, on areas of computer information protection;

7. Basic laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the field of computer law;

8. Dangers that children may encounter online, including topics on children's safe communication online (social networks, chats, forums), the basics of safe Internet journaling, Internet ethics and children's safe participation in online games;

9. Prevention of Internet addiction in children;

10. Computer viruses and security measures by inviting experts on the types of computer viruses, methods of their spread and measures to protect against the penetration and spread of viruses;

11. Software information protection, information storage rules.

Therefore, ensuring the information security of young people directly depends on the clarity of the goals and content, the level of education of the parents, as well as the young people themselves, in whose training both teachers of educational institutions and makhalla consultants on issues of spirituality and religious education play an important role. At the same time, maslahatchi's activities should be carried out through cooperation with various interested and responsible organizations, including internal affairs bodies.

In order to expand knowledge about information security among maslahatchis, it is necessary to conduct training seminars, give lectures for them and publish information in specialized media about work methods, the latest trends in the development of information security issues, expand their competencies in dealing with new technical and informational means of communication such as mobile phones, computers, tablets, players, satellite television, the Internet and others. Particular attention should be paid to the development of specialized websites for consultants where they can find information: about the age characteristics of children; on the psychological and pedagogical aspects of

education in the spirit of national traditions and universal human values; about methods of working with parents and adolescents to ensure information security; on the impact of information on the family to maintain peace stability in the country; about effective options for leisure activities and other things.

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